
A Study of Making Nonwoven Fabric as an Air Filter Based on Pineapple Leaf Fiber by Thermal Bonding Method

Syifa Hanifah^{1*}, and Giarto¹

¹ Politeknik STTT Bandung

* Correspondence: giartotaurus@yahoo.co.id; Tel.: -

Abstract

In this modern era, textile products that use natural fibers are more in demand because they offer various benefits such as renewable properties, excellent biodegradability and ease of manufacture that do not have a negative effect on the environment. Pineapple fiber is one of the natural fibers besides cotton which is used as raw material for air filter is flax fiber. This fiber is obtained from the leaves of pineapple plants by extraction, carried out to separate the cambium and fiber using a decorticator machine.

Pineapple (*Ananas comosus* L.) is one of the leading fruit commodities in Indonesia which leaves are leftover products. From research conducted by M. Asim, et al., (2015) it is known that the chemical composition and physical properties of pineapple fiber are close to the composition of flax fibers. So it is possible that pineapple fiber can be made into nonwoven which functions as an air filter such as flax fiber.

The experiment of making air filter nonwoven from pineapple fiber used thermal bonding method with the help of low melt polyester fiber as a bonding agent. The comparison of pineapple fiber and low melt polyester fiber used is 9: 1, then made with three variations of gramation 400, 500 and 600g / m². The thermal bonding process is carried out at a temperature of 130°C and pressed at a pressure of 25 bar for five minutes. Tests carried out include gramation, thickness, density, tensile strength, elongation, water permeability, porosity, pore size and filtering efficiency.

The testing results of nonwoven for air filters with three variations of gramation fabric have an effect on the dimensions and physical properties of the nonwoven produced. The greater the Gramation of fabric, the higher the thickness, density, strength, stretch and filtering efficiency and the greater the gramation of the fabric, the smaller the value of water permeability, porosity and pore size.

Keywords: air filter

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1. Introduction

Textiles are flexible materials made of woven yarn. Textiles are formed by means of embroidery, sewing, binding and pressing. In this modern era, textile products are increasingly varied, it is not only applied for clothes but also widely used for the construction of highway, agro-textile, medical, food and beverage, automotive, filter media and other product manufacturing industries.

Filter media is one of them is air filter for air purifier for household and industrial purposes. In this air filter, the use of textile materials is more often found in the form of nonwoven fabric with various types of fibers such as polyester and cotton with all its advantages and disadvantages.

Currently products that use natural fibers are more in demand because they offer various benefits such as renewable properties, excellent biodegradability and ease of manufacture that do not have a negative effect on the environment. Natural fibers, other than cotton used as raw material for air filters are flax fibers. One of the natural fibers that can be found in Indonesia is pineapple fiber or commonly called PALF (pineapple leaf fiber). The fiber is obtained from pineapple leaves. Pineapple leaves are waste because so far the consumption of pineapple is only the fruit. Utilization of pineapple fiber has so far been used to make clothing, but a larger amount is used to make ropes and twines (Robert R. Franck, 2005 p.322).

Pineapple (*Ananas comosus* L.) is one of the leading fruit commodities in Indonesia. This refers to the amount of pineapple production which occupies the third position after bananas and mangoes. The development of pineapple harvest area has increased even though it tends to slow down in the last five years, as well as its production. For the Southeast Asian region, Indonesia is the third largest producer of pineapple after the Philippines and Thailand with a contribution of around 23% (Nenas Outlook, 2016). The results of 2017 agricultural statistics show that pineapple production in Indonesia reaches 1,396,141 tons / year.

Based on the explanation above, it can be estimated that the use of pineapple fiber as raw material for air filter has a great opportunity in Indonesia. For this reason, a further study is needed to determine the physical properties of air filters with the raw material of pineapple fiber.

The purpose of this study is to determine the extent to which pineapple fibers can be processed into woven weaving by thermal bonding method which functions as an air filter. The purpose of this study is to produce a product that functions as an air filter on a water purifier that can be used at home or in industry with raw materials derived from pineapple fiber.

2. Experimental

2.1. Research Methods

To facilitate observation and compilation of data to be obtained, steps need to be taken that can be seen in Figure 2.1 below:

Source: Suryana. 2010. Research Methodology. Indonesian Education University

Figure 1. Research flow diagram

- 1) Observation (Study of literature)
At this stage a collection of theoretical references can be supported research to be conducted. References are obtained from books, journals and other sources.
- 2) Identify the scope of the problem
At this stage the most relevant and interesting problems to study are sought from the results of the literature study.
- 3) Hypothesis
At this stage a temporary answer is made to the research problem whose answer must be tested.
- 4) Research design
From the existing hypothesis, a research design is made so that the hypothesis can be answered scientifically.
- 5) Research
After making further research designs, the design was practiced
- 6) Data collection
At this stage, data is collected from the results of research and product testing
- 7) Analysis of data
Data from the results of testing and research were analyzed according to relevant theories to answer the hypothesis
- 8) Conclusion of results
The data that has been analyzed is then made a conclusion.

2.2. Tool Preparation

To make an air filter using the thermal bonding method, the tools used are as follows:

- 1) Mechanical softener machine

Softener machine functions to smooth the fiber mechanically, so that the fiber grip becomes smoother.

Machine specifications:

- Made in : Indonesia
- Top roll number : 8 units

- Bottom roll number : 8 units
- Rpm roll up and down : 21 rpm.

2) Cutting machine

The cutting machine serves to cut the filament fibers into staple fibers.

Machine specifications:

- Made in : Indonesia
- Rpm feed roll : 47 rpm
- Feed roll diameter : 100 mm
- Rpm knife : 47 rpm
- Size of fiber after being cut : 1.5 inches

3) Opener machine

Opener machine functions to open clumps or bales of fiber.

Machine specifications:

- Made in : Indonesia
- Number of beaters : 3 pieces
- Rpm beater : 500 rpm
- Beater diameter : 500 mm
- Rpm feed roll : 6 rpm
- Feed roll diameter : 60 mm
- Electricity : 5.6 kW
- Fiber size : 1.5 inches

4) Hot press machine

The hot press machine serves to increase the strength of nonwoven by being given a certain pressure at hot temperatures (maximum 25 °C) so that the low melt fibers will melt and stick with other fibers.

Machine specifications:

- Made in : Tesktil Center
- Plate size : 30 cm x 30 cm
- Maximum pressure : 1000 bars
- Maximum temperature : 250 °C

2.3. Material Preparation

The raw material used to make woven weaving cloth which functions as an air filter is a mixture of pineapple fiber and low melt polyester fiber which is a binding fiber with a ratio of 9:1.

The steps for preparing raw materials are carried out as follows:

1) Smoothing pineapple fibers

Pineapple fiber as much as 2.5 kg first through a mechanical smoothing process by grinding by 8 pairs of rollers on the softener machine. The grinding process is carried out four times or if the fiber surface is considered smooth enough.

Figure 2. Process of refining pineapple fibres

2) Cutting of pineapple fiber

After the pineapple fibers are mashed then the cutting process. Pineapple fibers measuring approximately 0.7 m are cut to 1.5 inches use a cutting machine.

Figure 3. Pineapple fibers after the cutting process

3) Opening of pineapple fiber

Pineapple fiber measuring 1.5 inches is then processed in an opener machine which functions to open the fibers that are still clumping. On the opener machine, pineapple fibers are passed on two beaters so that the clumping fibers will open.

Figure 4. Opener machine

4) Weighing of pineapple fibers and low melt polyester fibers

Each fiber is weighed according to the calculation formula, pineapple fiber 2,430 g (90%) and low melt polyester fiber 270 g (10%) so that the weight of the mixed raw material is 2,700 g.

5) Mixing of pineapple fibers and low melt polyester fibers

Mixing of pineapple fiber and low melt polyester fiber is carried out on the machine opener. Low melt polyester fibers are spread evenly over pineapple fibers in bribe lattice. After it feels quite even, the engine starts. The blending process involves two beaters and two feedings are carried out to ensure that the two fibers are evenly mixed.

Figure 5. (a) Mixing process (b) Mixing fibers

2.4. Making Nonwoven Samples

After preparing the tools and materials to be used, the next process is making samples which are done by:

1. Weighing mixed fibers The fiber that has gone through the blending process is then weighed with variations in weight of 40g, 50g and 60g.

Figure 6. The process of weighing mixed fibers

2. Making nonwoven with thermal bonding method

The weighed fiber is then arranged on a 32 cm x 32 cm pan which has been first coated with Teflon paper on the inside then the fiber is covered by other Teflon paper. Furthermore, the mixed fiber was pressurized as much as 25 bars and heated at 130 °C for five minutes with a hot press.

Figure 7. (a) Arrangement of raw materials (b) Thermal binding process

2.5 Nonwoven sample Testing

2.5.1 Testing of Nonwoven Gramation

Tests for nonwoven gramation refer to ASTM D 3776 - 96 (Standard Test Method for Mass Per Unit Area (Weight) of Fabric). The steps taken during testing are as follows:

- The sample cloth is cut to a size of 5 cm long and 5 cm wide
- Then the specimen is conditioned in a room with a temperature of 25 °C and humidity of 65% with a minimum time of 6 hours
- After being conditioned, the specimen is then weighed using a balance sheet with accuracy up to 0.1% of its mass
- After obtaining the weight then the value is calculated using the formula:

$$\text{Fabric weight (g/m}^2\text{)} = \frac{100 \text{ (cm/m)} \times 100 \text{ (cm/m)}}{\text{lenth (cm)} \times \text{width (cm)}} \times \text{weighing weight (g)}$$

2.5.2 Testing of Nonwoven Thickness

Testing of the thickness of nonwoven refers to ASTM D 5736 - 95 (Standard Test Method for Thickness of High Nonwoven Fabrics). The steps taken during testing are as follows:

- The sample cloth is cut to a size of 5 cm x 5 cm. Cut fabric must be free of folds, wrinkled or wrinkled.
- Then the specimen is conditioned at 25 °C and humidity is 65% with a minimum time of 6 hours
- After being conditioned, each side and the middle part of each specimen measured its thickness using a thickness tester, the thickness value was read to the accuracy of 0.02 mm.
- The results of the thickness value are then calculated on average, standard deviation, coefficient of variation, sampling error, maximum - minimum value and F test.

2.5.3 Testing of nonwoven Density

For testing the density of nonwoven gramation test data and fabric thickness are used. Gramation values and fabric thickness obtained from the test results are used to calculate the value of fabric density using the formula:

$$Density (Kg/m^3) = \frac{fabric\ weight\ per\ unit\ area\ (Kg/m^2)}{fabric\ thickness\ (m)}$$

2.5.4 Testing of The tensile strength and elongation

Testing of tensile strength and elongation of nonwoven refers to ASTM D 5034 - 08 (Standard Test Method for Breaking Strength and Elongation of Textile Fabrics (Grab Test)). The steps taken during testing are as follows:

- The sample cloth is cut to a size of 10 cm x 20 cm.
- Then the specimen is conditioned at 25 °C and humidity is 65% with a minimum time of 6 hours
- After being conditioned, the specimen is pulled up to tear using a tens lab tool with a 7.5 cm pinch distance, 2.5 cm clamp size and 300 ± 10 mm / min withdrawal speed.
- The results of the fabric tensile strength and elongation are then calculated on average, standard deviation, coefficient of variation, sampling error, maximum - minimum value and F test.

2.5.5 Testing of Nonwoven Permeability

Air permeability testing of nonwoven refers to ASTM D 737-96 (Standard Test Method for Air Permeability of Textile Fabrics). The steps taken during testing are as follows:

- The sample cloth is cut to a size of 30 cm x 30 cm
- Then the specimen is conditioned at 25 °C and humidity is 65% with a minimum time of 6 hours
- Once conditioned, specimens are subjected to air pressure using static air permeability test instruments. The pressure given is 200 Pa with a test area of 20 cm².

- The results of the fabric water permeability values are then calculated on average, standard deviation, coefficient of variation, sampling error, maximum - minimum value and F test.

2.5.6 Testing of Nonwoven Porosity

To get the porosity value of nonwoven using the value of the test results of fabric density and mixed fiber density values. Then the values are calculated using the following formula:

$$\emptyset (\%) = \frac{\rho_{fabric}}{\rho_{fiber}} \times 100\%$$

$$\varepsilon (\%) = (1 - \emptyset) \times 100\%$$

where :

ε = fabric porosity (%),

\emptyset = volume fraction of solid material (%)

ρ_{fabric} = fabric density (kg / m³)

ρ_{fiber} = fiber density (kg / m³)

2.5.7 Testing of Pore Size and Nonwoven Filtering Efficiency

Testing the size of the pores of the nonwoven refers to SNI 08-4418-97 (How to test the size of geotextile pores). The steps taken during testing are as follows:

- Sample cloth cut with a diameter of 25 cm.
- Then the specimen is conditioned at 25 °C and relative humidity (RH) 65% for 6 hours.
- The mesh container to be used is weighed first and recorded the weight as the weight of the empty container.
- The conditioned specimens are weighed by weight and the value is recorded as the empty filter weight.
- Grains with a specific mesh size are weighed as much as \pm 50g and the weight is recorded as the initial grain weight.
- The weighed filter is then mounted on an empty mesh container and the weighed granules are spread throughout the filter surface.
- Then the container is sifted for 15 minutes
- After 15 minutes the mesh container and filter are weighed again, the weight is recorded as mesh container weight + grain and filter weight + granules.
- The weighing results are used to calculate the size of the pore and filter filtering efficiency and then calculate the average, standard deviation, coefficient of variation, sampling error, maximum - minimum value and F test.

2.5.8 Testing Nonwoven Samples Test Results

2.5.8.1 Fabric Gramation Test Results

Table 1 is processing data from the results of testing the Gramation of fabric resulting from three variations.

Table 1. Data on the result of Gramation fabric testing

Item	Variation 1 (gramation 400 g/m ²)	Variation 2 (gramation 500 g/m ²)	Variation 3 (gramation 600 g/m ²)
	fabric wight (g/m ²)	fabric wight (g/m ²)	fabric wight (g/m ²)
N	10	10	10
\bar{x}	424,8590	529,3013	624,4054
Min	393,19	486,00	597,22
Max	454,86	569,85	681,96
S	18,19	25,184	30,100
CV	4,281	4,758	4,821
E	2,653	2,949	2,988
F _{count}	1,38	1,19	1,65
F _{Table}	3,18		

2.5.8.2 Fabric Thickness Test Results

Table 2. below is processing data from the results of testing the thickness of fabric resulting from three variations.

Table 2.2 Data on the result of thickness fabric testing

Item	Variation 1 (gramation 400 g/m ²)	Variation 2 (gramation 500 g/m ²)	Variation 3 (gramation 600 g/m ²)
	thickness (mm)	thickness (mm)	thickness (mm)
N	10	10	10
\bar{x}	1,78	2,16	2,49
Min	1,70	2,08	1,70
Max	1,91	2,28	2,62
S	0,08	0,07	0,08
CV	4,57	3,27	3,02
E	2,83	2,03	1,87
F _{count}	1,14	1,14	1,00
F _{Table}	3,18		

2.5.8.3 Fabric Density Test Results

Table 3 below is the processing of data from the results of fabric density testing resulting from three variations

Table 3. Data on the result of fabric density testing

Item	Variation 1 (gramation 400 g/m ²)	Variation 2 (gramation 500 g/m ²)	Variation 3 (gramation 600 g/m ²)
	density (Kg/m ³)	density (Kg/m ³)	density (Kg/m ³)
N	10	10	10
\bar{x}	239,65	245,49	250,87
Min	214,86	213,16	228,08
Max	262,03	265,05	267,44
S	14,53	15,60	11,85
CV	6,06	6,35	4,72
E	3,76	3,94	2,93
F _{count}	1,07	1,73	1,23
F _{Table}	3,18		

2.5.8.4 Tensile Strength Test Results

Table 4 below is processing data from the results of fabric strength testing resulting from three variations.

Table 4. Data on the result of fabric tensile strength testing

Item	Variation 1 (gramation 400 g/m ²)	Variation 2 (gramation 500 g/m ²)	Variation 3 (gramation 600 g/m ²)
	strength (N)	strength (N)	strength (N)
N	10	10	10
\bar{x}	169,28	209,42	333,03
Min	114,92	138,60	224,10
Max	240,03	298,99	483,02
S	43,86	59,01	80,50
CV	25,91	28,180	24,172
E	16,06	17,47	14,98
F _{count}	1,35	1,36	1,84
F _{Table}	3,18		

2.5.8.5 Fabric Elongation Test Results

Table 5 is processing data from the results of fabric elongation testing produced from three variations.

Table 5. Data on the result of fabric elongation testing

Item	Variation 1 (gramation 400 g/m ²)	Variation 2 (gramation 500 g/m ²)	Variation 3 (gramation 600 g/m ²)
	elongation (%)	elongation (%)	elongation (%)
N	10	10	10
\bar{x}	18,15	18,30	18,34
Min	10,40	11,41	9,79
Max	27,01	32,80	28,80
S	6,73	5,89	5,70
CV	37,13	32,16	31,09
E	23,01	19,93	19,27
F _{count}	1,14	1,03	1,18
F _{Table}	3,18		

2.5.8.6 Fabric Water Permeability Test Results

Table 6. below is processing data from the results of fabric water permeability testing resulting from three variations.

Table 6. Data on the result of fabric air permeability testing

Item	Variation 1 (gramation 400 g/m ²)	Variation 2 (gramation 500 g/m ²)	Variation 3 (gramation 600 g/m ²)
	<i>air permeability</i> (cm ³ /cm ² /s)	<i>air permeability</i> (cm ³ /cm ² /s)	<i>air permeability</i> (cm ³ /cm ² /s)
N	10	10	10
\bar{x}	183,60	135,40	109,90
Min	171,00	122,00	104,00
Max	199,00	150,00	116,00
Item	Variation 1 (gramation 400 g/m ²)	Variation 2 (gramation 500 g/m ²)	Variation 3 (gramation 600 g/m ²)
	<i>air permeability</i> (cm ³ /cm ² /s)	<i>air permeability</i> (cm ³ /cm ² /s)	<i>air permeability</i> (cm ³ /cm ² /s)
S	9,62	11,01	4,09
CV	5,24	8,13	3,73
E	3,25	5,04	2,31
F _{count}	1,14	2,69	2,35
F _{Table}	3,18		

2.5.8.7 Fabric Porosity Test Results

Table 7 below is processing data of the results of fabric porosity testing resulting from three variations of fabrication.

Table 7. Data on the result of fabric porosity test results

Item	Variation 1 (gramation 400 g/m ²)	Variation 2 (gramation 500 g/m ²)	Variation 3 (gramation 600 g/m ²)
	Porosity (%)	Porosity (%)	Porosity (%)
N	10	10	10
\bar{x}	91,78	91,58	91,40
Min	91,01	90,91	90,83
Max	92,63	92,69	92,18
S	0,50	0,53	0,41
CV	0,54	0,58	0,44
E	0,33	0,36	0,27
F _{hitung}	1,06	1,29	1,22
F _{tabel}	3,18		

2.5.8.8 Test Results for Fabric Pores

Table 8 below is the data processing results of testing the fabric pore size resulting from three variations. Each variation of nonwoven is tested with different grain sizes, if the weight of the granules that pass is less than 5%, the pore size of the nonwoven is the same as the size of the grain used. Testing the size of the pores of woven fabric refers to SNI 08-4418-97 (How to test the size of geotextile pores).

Table 8. Data on the result of fabric pores testing

Item	Variation 1 (gramation 400 g/m ²)	Variation 2 (gramation 500 g/m ²)	Variation 3 (gramation 600 g/m ²)
	tested with grain size (0,425 μ)	tested with grain size (0,355 μ)	tested with grain size (0,250 μ)
N	5	5	5
\bar{x}	4,567%	4,544%	3,679%
Min	4,29	4,37	3,04
Max	4,80	4,69	4,20
S	0,211	0,118	0,496
Item	Variation 1 (gramation 400 g/m ²)	Variation 2 (gramation 500 g/m ²)	Variation 3 (gramation 600 g/m ²)
	tested with grain size (0,425 μ)	tested with grain size (0,355 μ)	tested with grain size (0,250 μ)
CV	4,6612	2,594	13,483
E	4,043	2,274	11,817

F _{count}	1,79	4,20	2,35
F _{tabel}	6,39		

2.5.8.9 Filtering Efficiency Test Results

Table 9 below is the data processing test results of filtering efficiency resulting from three variations.

Table 9. Data on the result of filtering efficiency testing

Item	Variation 1 (gramation 400 g/m ²)	Variation 2 (gramation 500 g/m ²)	Variation 3 (gramation 600 g/m ²)
	Filtration efficiency for granules 0,425 μ (%)	Filtration efficiency for granules 0,355 μ (%)	Filtration efficiency for granules 0,250 μ (%)
N	5	5	5
\bar{x}	74,139	83,922	93,673
Min	73,52	83,66	92,73
Max	74,74	84,53	94,34
S	0,572	0,390	0,624
CV	0,771	0,465	0,666
E	0,676	0,408	0,584
F _{count}	1,47	1,60	1,09
F _{tabel}	6,39		

3. Results and Discussion

The discussion chapter is a discussion of the results of the experiments conducted. The data presented can be in the form of graphs and images of the test results. The graphs presented are graphs between the weight of the raw material and the other parameters of gramation.

The following will be elaborated on the discussion of experimental results on variations in fabric gramation and the process of fiber hand lay-up.

3.1. Fabric Gramation Test Results

The weight of nonwoven (or mass of fabric) is defined as the mass per unit area of cloth and is usually measured in g / m² (or gsm). From the results of the F test calculation shows the value of F_{count} < F_{tabel} value so that H₀ can be accepted which means that the value of variations 1, 2 and 3 are mutually influential and are in the same range. Can be seen in Figure 8, graph the results of the average of fabric gramation test shows the more raw materials used, the fabric produced is more tightly. This can be proven by the formula:

$$Fabric\ weight\ (g/m^2) = \frac{100\ (cm/m) \times 100\ (cm/m)}{lenth\ (cm) \times width\ (cm)} \times weighing\ weight\ (g)$$

Figure 8. The graph of average of Fabric Gramation

If the weight of the raw material in the same area is more then it will produce a heavier weight of fabric per unit area or in other words the fabric produced is denser, conversely if the weight of the raw material in the same area is less then the fabric produced will be tenuous.

3.2. Fabric Thickness Test Results

Figure 9. The graph of average of Fabric Thickness

Fabric thickness is defined as the distance between two fabric surfaces under the specified applied pressure. From the results of the F test calculation shows the value of $F_{count} < F_{table}$ value so that H_0 can be accepted which means that the value of variations 1, 2 and 3 are mutually influential and are in the same range. Can be seen in Figure 9 graph of the average of fabric thickness that the greater the fabric gramation, the thicker the fabric. This is because when raw materials of different weights are arranged in a container with the same area, the composition of the raw material will increase in a high direction so that the thickness will increase.

3.3. Fabric Density Test Results

Figure 10. The graph of average of Fabric Density

The density of the fabric is defined as the measured weight per unit area (kg / m²) divided by the thickness of the fabric measured from the fabric (m). From the results of the F test calculation shows the value of $F_{count} < F_{table}$ value so that H_0 can be accepted which means that the value of variations 1, 2 and 3 are mutually influential and are in the same range. It can be seen in Figure 10 the graph of the average results of the fabric density test found that the greater the value of fabric Gramation then the density will be higher. This is due to the increasing amount of fiber (raw material is getting heavier) in a volume of the same object which causes the distance between fibers to be increasingly tight.

3.4. Test Results for Tensile Strength

Figure 11. The graph of average Tensile Strength of Fabric

According to S.J. Russel (2007), the stress-strain properties of nonwoven are determined by the orientation distribution of fiber segments. From the results of the F test calculation shows the value of $F_{count} < F_{table}$ value so that H_0 can be accepted which means that the value of variations 1, 2 and 3 are mutually influential and are in the same range. Figure 11 the graph of the average of tensile strength

of the fabric shows that the greater the gramation of the fabric, the greater the value of tensile strength. This is due to the increasing number of fibers in the same area, when the amount of fiber is large, there will be a lot of fiber orientation distribution. When large amounts of fiber in one area are tied together using a method, when the resulting fabric is pulled up to cause the fabric to tear the tensile strength value will be large.

3.5. Fabric Elongation Testing Results

Figure 12. The graph of average of Fabric Elongation

According to NM Susyami Hitariat, et al. (2005), the stretch of cloth is interpreted as the increase in fabric length when the fabric is broken compared to the original fabric length expressed in percent (%). The values of variations 1, 2 and 3 are mutually influential and are in the same range. In Figure 12, the graph of the average of fabric elongation shows that the higher the gramation of the fabric, the higher the elongation value. This is because the bond points at each Gramation are increasing, if the bond point increases with increasing gramation, the tensile strength of the fabric will also increase, this will affect the the fabric elongation.

3.6. Fabric Air Permeability Test Results

Figure 13. The graph of average of Fabric Air Permeability

From the results of the calculation of the F test shows the value of $F_{count} < F_{table}$ value so that H_0 can be accepted which means that the value of variations 1, 2 and 3 affect each other. It can be seen from Figure 13 the graph of the average of fabric air permeability, that the greater the fabric gramation, the smaller the value of air permeability. This is because the weight and thickness of the fabric determines the fabric density which determines the proportion of the cavity in the fabric structure produced. The denser the fabric, the smaller the proportion of the cavity in the fabric, if the proportion of the fabric cavity is small then the air will be difficult to pass through the fabric.

3.7. Fabric Porosity Test Results

Figure 14. The graph of average of Fabric Porosity

According to S.J. Russell (2007) the weight and thickness of the fabric determines the density of the fabric which also affects the freedom of movement of the fiber and determines the porosity of the fabric (proportion of cavities) in the structure of the nonwoven. Porosity provides information about the overall pore volume of porous material and is defined as the ratio of non-solid volume (vacuum) to the total volume of nonwoven. (%). From the results of the F test calculation shows the value of $F_{count} < F_{table}$ value so that H_0 can be accepted which means that the value of variations 1, 2 and 3 are mutually influential and are in the same range. Can be seen in Figure 14 above the lower the higher the value of fabric gramation, the lower the value of porosity. This is in accordance with the theory given by S.J Russell and can be proven by the formula:

$$\phi (\%) = \frac{\rho_{fabric}}{\rho_{fiber}} \times 100\%$$

$$\varepsilon (\%) = (1 - \phi) \times 100\%$$

If the density of fabric is a large while the fiber density value is a dividing factor has a fixed value, the value of ϕ will also be large which will then affect the value of ε which is the reduction factor will be greater so that the value of ε will be smaller.

3.8. Results of Testing of Fabric Pore Size

Figure 15. The graph of average of Fabric Pore Size

According to S.J. Russel (2007) open pore size is important to determine the filtering performance and blockage of nonwoven and allows the determination of the filtering power of the nonwoven (%). From the results of the F test calculation shows the value of $F_{count} < F_{table}$ value so that H_0 can be accepted which means that the value of variations 1, 2 and 3 are mutually influential and are in the same range. Can be seen in Figure 15, the value of the pore size gets smaller with the increase in fabric gramation. This is influenced by the gramation and thickness of the fabric which then becomes a determinant of fabric density. When the fabric has a high density, the open pore size will be less because the amount of fiber that binds more and more, on the contrary if the fabric density is low then the open pore size will increase because the number of fibers that binds less and less.

3.9. Filtering Efficiency Test Results

Figure 16. The graph of average of Filtering Efficiency

From the results of the F test calculation shows the value of $F_{\text{count}} < F_{\text{table}}$ value so that H_0 can be accepted which means that the value of variations 1, 2 and 3 are mutually influential and are in the same range. It can be seen in Figure 16 the graph of the testing results, filtering efficiency shows that the higher the value of gramation, the higher the filtering efficiency. This is due to the density which then affects the size of the pores of the nonwoven. If the fabric gets denser, the porosity and pore size will be smaller, according to the theory of fabric porosity and pore size, so that when particles larger than 0.425μ pass through the air filter, more particles will be held back in air filter cloth with a pore size of $0,250\mu$.

3.10. The ability of pineapple fiber as an air filter

From the results of all tests that have been carried out include gramation, thickness and density affecting tensile strength, elongation, porosity, air permeability, pore size and filtering efficiency which can then influence the filtering capacity of the nonwoven. With different pore sizes of 0.425μ , 0.355μ and 0.250μ and associated with specific size data for indoor air contamination (national air filtration association, V6 2010), all three variations of pineapple fiber air filter cloth (90%) and low melt polyester fibers (10%) that have been made will be able to filter contaminants such as bacteria, cigarette smoke particles, kitchen smoke particles or oil, dander, dust, insecticide dust, coal dust, plant spores, fertilizers and hairs that have a size of $0, 5 - 100\mu$ with filtering efficiency 74.139%, 83.922% and 93.67%.

4. Conclusion

- 1) The results of the analysis of the dimensions and physical properties of nonwoven that have been made show:
 - The more weight the raw material is weighed, the greater the value of the gramation.
 - The greater the value of gramation of the nonwoven, the higher the value of thickness, density, tensile strength, elongation and filtering efficiency of the nonwoven.
 - The greater the value of gramation of nonwoven, the smaller the value of air permeability, porosity and pore size.
- 2) Based on the results of testing and discussion, pineapple fiber can be used as an alternative raw material in making air filter fabric.

5. Suggestions

For further research, if using raw materials and the same binding method, it is better to go through a web-making process to obtain a better nonwoven and chemical properties testing and field tests to find out more specific uses and filters for air filter nonwoven

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